

Cardiometabolic Complications of Cushing's Syndrome: Mechanism and Management – A Systematic review

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Cushing's syndrome (CS), caused by chronic endogenous or exogenous glucocorticoid excess, is associated with a severe cardiometabolic phenotype and increased cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Many complications persist even after biochemical remission, highlighting the need for comprehensive long-term management. **Objective:** To systematically review the epidemiology, pathophysiological mechanisms, clinical assessment, and management strategies for cardiometabolic complications in CS, and to identify gaps in current evidence. **Methods:** A systematic literature search was conducted in PubMed, Embase, Scopus, and Google Scholar for studies published up to 2025, in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. Eligible articles included observational studies, interventional trials, systematic reviews, and guidelines addressing cardiovascular and metabolic outcomes in CS. Data were extracted and synthesized qualitatively across predefined domains. **Results:** CS is characterized by resistant hypertension, visceral obesity, insulin resistance and diabetes, dyslipidemia, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, a prothrombotic state, and accelerated atherosclerosis. These abnormalities result from multifactorial glucocorticoid effects on metabolism, vasculature, and inflammation. Although definitive control of cortisol improves outcomes, residual cardiometabolic risk frequently persists after remission. Targeted management of blood pressure, glycaemia, lipids, and thrombotic risk, along with perioperative thromboprophylaxis and rehabilitation, is essential for risk reduction. **Conclusions:** Cardiometabolic complications are major determinants of morbidity and mortality in CS. Normalization of cortisol alone is often insufficient; an integrated, long-term strategy addressing persistent metabolic and vascular dysfunction is required. Further high-quality prospective studies are needed to define optimal post-remission management and long-term outcomes.

Keywords: *Cushing's syndrome, hypercortisolism, hypertension, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, venous thromboembolism, cardiovascular risk, management*

INTRODUCTION:

Cushing's syndrome (CS) results from prolonged exposure to supraphysiologic cortisol, whether exogenous (glucocorticoid therapy) or endogenous (ACTH-secreting pituitary adenomas Cushing disease ectopic ACTH, or adrenal cortisol-producing lesions). Although the classic phenotype includes central obesity, skin thinning, and myopathy, it is the cardiometabolic complications hypertension, dysglycaemia, dyslipidaemia, prothrombotic state and accelerated atherosclerosis that most strongly drive morbidity and premature mortality. Prompt identification and normalization of cortisol exposure are pivotal to reduce cardiometabolic harm, yet many adverse cardiometabolic effects may persist or partially reverse only slowly after biochemical cure, necessitating long-

term multidisciplinary care (Nieman et al.; Fleseriu et al.).^{1,2} Cushing's syndrome is associated with increased mortality due to cardiovascular complications, particularly hypertension and metabolic syndrome, which may persist after remission. Both endogenous cortisol excess and prolonged exogenous corticosteroid use contribute to sustained cardiovascular risk (Isidori AM et al.).³ Insulin resistance underlies obesity, metabolic syndrome, and type 2 diabetes and reflects reduced insulin action in key metabolic tissues. Glucocorticoids increase lipolysis, proteolysis, and hepatic gluconeogenesis while inhibiting glucose uptake. These changes result in elevated blood glucose levels (Geer EB et al.).⁴ Cushing's syndrome most commonly results from exogenous steroid use, with endogenous cases occurring in 2–8 per million annually.

It is associated with hyperglycaemia, catabolism, immunosuppression, hypertension, weight gain, and neuropsychiatric changes (Reincke M et al.).⁵

METHODS:

Study Design and Search Strategy:

A systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines. Databases searched included PubMed, Embase, Scopus, and Google Scholar for studies published between January 1997 and September 2025 using the following keywords:

“Cushing’s syndrome,” “hypercortisolism,” “cardiometabolic,” “insulin resistance,” “hypertension,” “dyslipidaemia,” “obesity,” “cardiovascular disease,” and “management.”

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion:

- Observational (cohort, cross-sectional, case-control) or interventional studies
- Reviews and clinical guidelines discussing cardiometabolic aspects of CS

- Studies published in English

Exclusion:

- Case reports, animal studies, editorials
- Studies unrelated to metabolic or cardiovascular outcomes

Data Extraction and Quality Assessment:

Two reviewers independently screened and extracted data on population characteristics, metabolic and cardiovascular parameters, and therapeutic outcomes. The Newcastle Ottawa Scale (NOS) was used for cohort studies, and AMSTAR-2 for systematic reviews.

Data Synthesis:

Data were synthesized narratively and categorised into three thematic domains:

1. Mechanistic pathways
2. Clinical cardiometabolic complications
3. Management and outcomes

Records identified through database searching
(PubMed, Embase, Scopus, Google Scholar)
(n = 1,236)

Records after duplicates removed
(n = 924)
Duplicates removed
(n = 312)

Screening
Records screened (title & abstract)
(n = 924)

Records excluded
(n = 812)

- Not related to cardiometabolic outcomes
- Case reports / editorials
- Animal studies
- Non-English articles

Eligibility
Full-text articles assessed for eligibility
(n = 104)

Full-text articles excluded
(n = 85)

- No relevant cardiometabolic data (n = 38)
- Inadequate methodology or data (n = 27)
- Overlapping populations (n = 12)
- Narrative opinions / non-systematic reports (n = 8)

Included
Studies included in qualitative synthesis
(n = 19)

Epidemiology and clinical burden:

Endogenous CS is rare (roughly 1.8–3.2 cases per million per year in classical estimates), but its cardiometabolic burden is disproportionately large. Hypertension affects up to 70–80% of patients during active disease; impaired glucose tolerance or diabetes occurs in 20–50%; dyslipidaemia, visceral adiposity and NAFLD (Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease) are common; and venous thromboembolism (VTE) incidence is markedly increased particularly in the peridiagnostic and perioperative periods. Large cohort and registry studies consistently demonstrate elevated risks of myocardial infarction, stroke and VTE and increased all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in untreated disease; mortality declines after remission but frequently remains above population norms in multicentre follow-ups. (Dekkers et al.; Stuijver et al.; Lambert et al.; Bengtsson et al.; Mondin et al.).^{6,7,8,9,10}

Pathophysiological mechanisms linking excess cortisol to cardiometabolic disease:

Hyperglucocorticoidism produces cardiometabolic disease through multiple overlapping mechanisms which operate at molecular, tissue and organ-system levels. Major pathways follow.

1. Blood pressure regulation, sodium handling and vascular dysfunction:

Glucocorticoids increase vascular sensitivity to vasoconstrictors (catecholamines, angiotensin II), downregulate endothelial nitric oxide bioavailability, and promote arterial stiffness and remodeling. Renally, cortisol increases sodium reabsorption and expands intravascular volume; when the capacity of 11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 2 (11 β -HSD2) is exceeded, cortisol can act at mineralocorticoid receptors to produce a mineralocorticoid-like phenotype (sodium retention, hypokalaemia). These mechanisms combine to produce frequent, often severe and sometimes resistant hypertension in CS. (Isidori et al.; Bailey et al.).^{3,11}

2. Insulin resistance, hepatic gluconeogenesis and pancreatic β -cell effects:

Glucocorticoids increase hepatic gluconeogenesis by upregulating enzymes (PEPCK {phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase}, G6Pase {Glucose-6-phosphatase}), reduce peripheral glucose uptake (skeletal muscle insulin signalling is impaired), and increase lipolysis with consequent flux of free fatty acids to the liver. Chronic exposure also adversely affects β -cell function and mass in some patients. The net effect is systemic insulin resistance with impaired glucose tolerance and increased risk of overt diabetes; severity depends on cortisol dose, duration and individual susceptibility. (Geer et al.; Mondin A et al.).^{4,10}

3. Adipose tissue redistribution and pro-inflammatory adipokine profile:

Cortisol favors visceral adipogenesis while causing peripheral muscle catabolism the classic central obesity and sarcopenia of CS. Visceral adipose tissue secretes proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6 {interleukin-6}, TNF- α {Tumor Necrosis Factor -alpha}), adipokine dysregulation (e.g., low adiponectin), and prothrombotic mediators that amplify insulin resistance, endothelial dysfunction and atherogenesis. Adipose-specific amplification of glucocorticoid action (11 β -HSD1 {11 β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase type 1} activity) further concentrates effects within visceral depots. (Geer et al.; Bavaresco et al.; Dadej et al.).^{4,12,13}

4. Dyslipidaemia and hepatic steatosis (NAFLD):

Hypercortisolism promotes lipolysis with increased hepatic free fatty acid influx, increases VLDL production, and alters lipoprotein metabolism \rightarrow elevated triglycerides, frequently elevated LDL and reduced HDL in many series. These perturbations, together with insulin resistance, predispose to NAFLD and an atherogenic lipid profile that increases ASCVD (atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease) risk. (Reincke et al. ; Sun et al.).^{5,14}

5. Hypercoagulability and thrombosis:

CS creates a prothrombotic milieu: increased coagulation factor levels (e.g., factor VIII, fibrinogen), elevated plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1), platelet activation and impaired fibrinolysis. Observational cohorts show substantially increased VTE risk particularly in the first year after diagnosis and around surgery and VTE is a major contributor to morbidity and early mortality in CS. (Stuijver et al.; Koraćević et al.; Wagner et al.).^{7,15,16}

6. Persistent vascular and metabolic injury after remission:

Normalization of cortisol often improves metabolic indices, but structural vascular changes (atherosclerosis, arterial stiffness), persistent visceral adiposity and incomplete β -cell recovery can leave residual cardiometabolic risk. Long-term cohort studies indicate reductions in but not complete normalization of mortality, particularly in patients with delayed cure, persistent disease or long pre-diagnosis exposure. (Bengtsson et al.; Mondin et al.; Ragnarsson et al.).^{9,10,17}

Clinical assessment: baseline and follow-up:

Baseline evaluation at diagnosis:

At initial presentation, clinicians should perform a comprehensive cardiometabolic assessment: office and ambulatory blood pressure, orthostatic measures and serum potassium; fasting glucose, HbA1c and/or an oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT - OGTT may be more

sensitive to detect glucocorticoid-related dysglycaemia); full fasting lipid panel; liver tests and imaging if NAFLD suspected; BMI and waist circumference; ECG and consideration of echocardiography in symptomatic patients; and assessment for VTE risk factors. Because traditional cardiovascular risk calculators underestimate risk in hypercortisolism, clinicians should interpret them conservatively and plan early aggressive management when risk factors are present. (Endocrine Society Guideline Nieman et al.; Fleseriu et al.).^{1,2}

Ongoing monitoring after treatment:

After definitive therapy and/or medical control, repeat assessments at defined intervals are recommended to track recovery and manage residual risk: blood pressure and electrolytes, glycaemic indices, lipid profile and liver health, body composition and muscle function, and screening for recurrent hypercortisolism. Multidisciplinary follow-up (endocrinology, cardiology, diabetes services, dietetics, physiotherapy) is strongly advised for tailored risk reduction and rehabilitation. (Fleseriu et al.; Reincke et al.).^{2,5}

Management strategies: general principles and targeted therapy:

1. Definitive control of hypercortisolism the priority:

Restoration of eucortisolism is the most effective intervention to reduce cortisol-driven cardiometabolic harm. First-line therapy for endogenous CS is surgical removal of the source (transsphenoidal pituitary surgery for Cushing disease; adrenalectomy for unilateral cortisol-producing adenomas). Medical therapies steroidogenesis inhibitors (ketoconazole, metyrapone, osilodrostat), pituitary-directed agents (pasireotide, cabergoline), and glucocorticoid receptor antagonists (mifepristone) have roles pre-operatively, when surgery is contraindicated, or for persistent/recurrent disease. Radiotherapy and bilateral adrenalectomy are reserved for refractory disease in selected cases. Prompt control reduces cardiometabolic events, but many patients require ongoing cardiovascular risk management. (Nieman et al.; Fleseriu et al.).^{1,2}

2. Hypertension: approach and drug choices:

Given the multifactorial etiology, blood pressure control often requires combination therapy. Lifestyle measures (sodium restriction, weight loss) are adjunctive but usually insufficient. Pharmacologic choices:

- **ACE inhibitors (Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors) / ARBs (Angiotensin II receptor blockers)** : recommended as first-line given renal and vascular protective effects and favourable metabolic profile.
- **Calcium channel blockers (CCBs)**: effective vasodilators used as add-on therapy.
- **Mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists (spironolactone/epirenone)**: particularly

useful when hypokalemia or mineralocorticoid-like features are seen.

- **Beta-blockers, diuretics**: used per standard indications and comorbidities. Resistant hypertension often improves after cure but may persist; drug interactions with steroidogenesis inhibitors and adrenal insufficiency after surgery require careful monitoring. (Isidori et al.).³

3. Glucose abnormalities: detection and therapy:

OGTT is sensitive for identifying steroid-related dysglycaemia, treatment goals should be individualized. Metformin is a common first-line agent for insulin resistance unless contraindicated. However, many patients especially with severe hypercortisolism require insulin for rapid glycaemic control. Emerging cardioprotective agents (GLP-1 {Glucagon-like peptide 1} receptor agonists and SGLT2 {sodium-glucose cotransporter-2} inhibitors) are attractive adjuncts for weight- and risk-reduction but require cautious use and more evidence in CS populations (risk of volume depletion or adrenal insufficiency with SGLT2 inhibitors; hyperglycaemia complexity with mifepristone). After restoration of eucortisolism, glycaemia often improves but regular reassessment is necessary. (Geer et al.; Mondlin A et al.).^{4,10}

4. Lipids, NAFLD and weight management:

Initiate statin therapy according to established ASCVD risk and LDL targets; many clinicians favour early lipid-lowering because CS confers high absolute risk. Lifestyle interventions (dietary counselling, supervised exercise, resistance training to address sarcopenia) are critical. Pharmacologic weight-loss options (GLP-1 receptor agonists) and bariatric surgery may be considered for persistent severe obesity, acknowledging limited CS-specific trial data. Targeting insulin resistance (metformin, pioglitazone in selected cases) can benefit triglycerides and hepatic steatosis; NAFLD should be monitored and managed per hepatology guidance. (Reincke et al.; Sun et al.).^{5,14}

5. Thrombosis prevention and perioperative management:

Because VTE risk is elevated particularly near diagnosis and around surgery clinicians should perform individualized thrombosis risk assessments and apply pharmacologic thromboprophylaxis (e.g., low-molecular-weight heparin) perioperatively for most patients unless contraindicated. Several cohort studies and reviews advocate for heightened awareness and extended prophylaxis in high-risk patients; however, formal randomized data are lacking and practice varies. (Stuijver et al.; Koraćević et al.; Wagner et al.).^{7,15,16}

6. Rehabilitation, sarcopenia and psychosocial care:

Muscle wasting and reduced exercise capacity are common and may persist after biochemical cure. Early physiotherapy, resistance training, nutritional optimisation, treatment of hypogonadism where present, and psychological support for mood and cognitive sequelae are recommended to improve functional outcomes and cardiometabolic health. (Ragnarsson et al. ; Braun LT et al.).^{17, 18} CS is associated with atypical depressive disorder (AD) symptomatology, which gradually improves with time after correction of hypercortisolism. Health care providers should be aware of changes in symptomatology (Dorn LD et al.)¹⁹

Outcomes after treatment: reversibility and residual risk:

Normalization of cortisol leads to improvement in blood pressure, glycaemic control and lipid markers in many patients sometimes within months. However, recovery is heterogeneous: established atherosclerotic plaques, arterial stiffness and persistent central adiposity may not fully reverse. Longitudinal and nationwide cohort studies demonstrate a decline in excess mortality after successful treatment but persistent elevation of cardiovascular risk in many series, especially when remission is delayed or incomplete. These data underscore the need for lifelong surveillance and aggressive management of residual cardiometabolic risk even after endocrine cure. (Lambert et al.; Bengtsson et al.; Mondin A et al.; Ragnarsson et al.).^{8,9,10,17}

Gaps in evidence and future research priorities:

1. **Randomized trials of cardiometabolic therapies in CS:** There is a paucity of CS-specific RCTs (Randomized control trials) testing GLP-1 RAs, SGLT2 inhibitors, novel lipid agents or anti-inflammatory interventions.
2. **Thromboprophylaxis strategies:** Clearer guideline evidence on perioperative and extended VTE prophylaxis is needed.
3. **Biomarkers of reversible vs irreversible damage:** Predictors that distinguish which patients will recover cardiometabolic health after remission would guide resource allocation.
4. **Mechanistic studies of persistent vascular dysfunction:** To develop targeted vascular therapies for patients with residual risk.
5. **Harmonized long-term follow-up protocols and registry collaboration:** To collect the numbers required to power interventional studies in this rare disorder. (Fleseriu et al.; Bavaresco et al.).^{2,12}

Practical clinical algorithm short checklist:

1. **At diagnosis:** full cardiometabolic assessment (BP, potassium, ECG, OGTT/HbA1c, lipid panel, LFTs, BMI/waist). (Nieman et al.; Fleseriu et al.).^{1,2}
2. **Immediate actions:** address severe hypertension and hyperglycaemia; plan definitive therapy for cortisol excess (surgery preferred when feasible).
3. **Perioperative:** individualized VTE risk assessment and pharmacologic prophylaxis for most patients undergoing surgery.
4. **After remission:** reassess and continue targeted therapies (antihypertensives, statins, glucose-lowering agents, rehabilitation) as indicated; schedule long-term follow-up.

CONCLUSION:

Cushing's syndrome produces severe, multifactorial cardiometabolic complications through direct glucocorticoid effects on vascular tone, renal sodium handling, insulin signalling, adipose tissue biology, hepatic lipid metabolism and coagulation. Definitive control of cortisol is the cornerstone of management, but many patients require aggressive, guideline-based management of blood pressure, glucose and lipids, perioperative vigilance for thrombosis, and structured rehabilitation. Because residual cardiometabolic risk frequently persists after biochemical cure, lifelong multidisciplinary follow-up is essential. Future research should prioritize randomized studies of cardiometabolic therapeutics in CS, standardized thromboprophylaxis protocols, and biomarkers of reversibility. (Nieman et al.; Fleseriu et al.; Isidori et al.; Geer et al.).^{1,2,3,4}

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Conflict of interest Author's have no conflict of interest

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